

A ferrocene tagged novel organic moiety : Synthesis, crystal structure and electrochemical aspects

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Abstract : Reaction of 2-(2-aminoethyl)pyridine (L) with ferrocenecarboxaldehyde (FCAL) in toluene gives rise to LH, the 1 : 1 Schiff base condensate of L and FCAL. Reduction of LH with NaBH₄ in methanol and subsequent protonation with stoichiometric proportion of hydrochloric acid enables to isolate the ferrocene bearing organometallic moiety, [LH₂]Cl.H₂O. Replacement of the counter anion, chloride, by hexafluorophosphate in acetone afforded the target ferrocene appended organometallic precursor, [LH₂]PF₆.H₂O with satisfactory yield. [LH₂]PF₆.H₂O is characterized by C, H and N microanalyses, FT-IR, ¹H NMR and ESI-MS and cyclic voltammetry. The X-ray crystal structure of it has also been determined. The structure reveals that it is centrosymmetric (space group *P2₁/c*).

Keywords : 2-(2-aminoethyl)pyridine, ferrocenecarboxaldehyde, Schiff base, organometallic moiety, centrosymmetric molecule.

Introduction

Ferrocene derivatives are unique monoelectron reservoir complexes. Consequently in redox-catalytic reactions they are potential mediators as well¹. Organic moieties with tagged redox center(s) like ferrocene are promising for developing molecular electronic devices, efficient artificial photosynthetic systems, organic liquid crystal light emitting devices and interesting electrochemical sensors². Ferrocene derivatives have also been exploited extensively in various D- π -A systems with the aim of studying charge transfer (CT) processes to design new material for non-linear optics and related applications². Due to the specific properties of the ferrocenium cation, these redox tagged moieties are also promising anti-tumor agents³. Both in organic and aqueous milieu, they are electrochemical sensors of cations, anions and even neutral molecules⁴. Transition metal complexes of these short of ligands have wider applications, for example as polymerization catalysts⁵, chiral catalysts⁶, molecular receptors⁷, molecular mag-

nets⁸. In addition, the conformational freedom of ferrocene and a large number of polarized C-H systems making C-H $\cdots\pi$ weak interactions important in crystal packing afford opportunities for generating novel topologies⁸. This aspect has kindled our interest to develop novel organic moieties with standard (ferrocene) redox attachment. Herein, we report the synthesis, structure and electrochemical features of a novel ferrocene tagged organic salt.

Results and discussion

In the course of our continuing research work on ferrocenyl chemistry, we have isolated a precursor salt having appended ferrocenyl moiety. Schiff base condensation of 2-(2-aminoethyl)pyridine with ferrocenecarboxaldehyde (FCAL) in equimolar proportion in toluene in presence of molecular sieves (4 Å), gives rise to a dark yellow pasty mass as a condensate in good yield. Subsequent reduction of the imine nitrogen (C=N) bond of this

Schiff base condensate with NaBH_4 in methanol at room temperature afforded a straw yellow mass. To isolate this reduced product, we protonated the generated amine nitrogen with stoichiometric proportion of HCl maintaining the pH 5 to 6. The synthetic scheme is outlined below :

839 cm^{-1} with a sharp yet medium intensity band at 558 cm^{-1} are due to $\nu(\text{PF}_6)$ vibration. The $-\text{NH}-$ band is observed at 3255 cm^{-1} . The band attributed to $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ vibration is noticeable at 3474 cm^{-1} . A moderate intensity band at 1459 cm^{-1} is due to pyridyl ring vibrations. The

For crystallization of the salt, we have converted this chloro salt to the corresponding hexafluorophosphate salt with NH_4PF_6 in a suspension of the chloro salt in acetone. The hexafluorophosphate salt was obtained as a dirty reddish-yellow precipitate. Shining red stick-like crystals suitable for X-ray crystal structure determination were obtained by direct diffusion of petroleum ether ($40\text{--}60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) into a moderately concentrated solution of the salt in dichloromethane at room temperature.

expected C-C stretching vibrations in the ferrocenyl ring are discernable at 1420 and 1106 cm^{-1} . Bands at 1002 cm^{-1} and 1030 cm^{-1} are due to the diagnostic bending vibrations of the ferrocene group⁹. The significant cyclopentadienyl (Cp) ring tilting vibration in Fe-Cp moiety¹⁰ is observed at 482 cm^{-1} .

In FT-IR spectrum, a very broad and sharp band at

The electrospray ionization mass spectrum (ESI-MS) of $[\text{LH}_2]\text{PF}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in methanol (Fig. 1) in a positive ionization mode exhibits a signal at m/z 321.0515 corresponding to $[\text{LH}_2]^+$ (calcd. 321.018). Signal at m/z of

Fig. 1. ESI-MS of $[\text{LH}_2]\text{PF}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in methanol.

198.9863 with 100% intensity is indicative of $[\text{FcCH}_2]^+$ (calcd. 198.938). In ESI-MS, the signal obtained at the highest m/z value of 519.022 is assigned as $[\text{LH} + \text{FcCH}_2]^+$ (calcd. 518.948).

In ^1H NMR spectrum (Fig. 2) of $[\text{LH}_2]\text{PF}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in CDCl_3 important signals appear in the range of 3–9 ppm. The ferrocenyl protons resonate in the expected region with expected patterns¹¹.

Fig. 2. 300 MHz ^1H NMR spectrum of the molecule $[\text{LH}_2]\text{PF}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in CDCl_3 . The sharp peak(s) at 7.26 ppm is due to the residual proton in CDCl_3 .

A PLATON view of the ferrocenium compound with atom numbering scheme is shown in Fig. 3. Selected bond distances and bond angles are given in Table 2. Significant hydrogen bonding data are given in Table 3. The crystallographic asymmetric unit of the compound consists of discrete ferrocenium moiety and a PF_6 unit. These ferrocenium and PF_6 units are linked together by intermolecular $\text{N9-H9} \cdots \text{O1}$ hydrogen bond. The carbon-nitrogen distances in the pyridine rings are almost identical 1.314(18) Å and 1.349(19) Å. This is virtually identical with the C–N distance of 1.340 Å, reported for pyridine. The slightly different bond lengths for the single and double bonds of the rings may be attributed to the electron donating ability of the ferrocenyl group and the π electron delocalization in the molecule. The two Cp rings in the same ferrocene moiety are parallel, with the dihedral angle between the two rings being 0.98°. The Fe–C bond lengths, 2.024(14) to 2.062(13) Å are all in

the expected range, but are slightly shorter compared with an average Fe–C bond length of 2.050 Å. The Cp planes and pyridine rings are almost orthogonal with the dihedral angles between them are 93.11° and 92.30° respectively. It is pertinent to note that the ferrocene moieties have orthogonal orientations as found in the crystal of pure ferrocene. The average Fe–C_{ring} distance in free ferrocene is of 2.04 Å¹².

Many potential nonlinear optical compounds form centrosymmetric crystals and consequently they do not exhibit second harmonic generation in the solid state. In order to circumvent this problem, a cocrystallization strategy has been proposed by Masse *et al.*¹³. Since our ferrocenyl salt, $[\text{LH}_2]\text{PF}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is centrosymmetric (space group $P2_1/c$), we do not expect it to manifest second harmonic generation in the crystalline state.

The electrochemical behaviour of the title compound has been studied by cyclic voltammetry (CV). In CV (Fig. 4) in acetonitrile, the compound $[\text{LH}_2]\text{PF}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ gives voltammogram with ferrocene based oxidation appearing at $E_{1/2}$ 596.5 mV vs Ag/Ag^+ at 100 mV s^{-1} scan rate. Here, the ratio of cathodic to anodic peak current values (i_{pc}/i_{pa}) comes out to be 1.027, close to unity. This is indicative of the idealistic reversible electron transfer behaviour.

Fig. 3. PLATON diagram of the ferrocenium compound showing the atom numbering scheme.

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram of $[LH_2]PF_6 \cdot H_2O$ in MeCN (concentration, 1.1 mM) 0.1 M in TBAP at a Pt electrode at a scan rate of 100 mV s^{-1} .

In summary, a novel organometallic compound bearing the standard redox centre (ferrocene) has been synthesized and successfully characterized. A heteroatomic unit like pyridine is linked to the ferrocenyl unit through a tailor made yet flexible molecular spacer. Thus this may serve as a potential ligand having standard redox attachment.

Experimental

Material and method :

Ferrocenecarboxaldehyde, 98%, 2-(2-aminoethyl)-pyridine, 95% and ammonium hexafluorophosphate, 95% were procured from Aldrich (USA). GR grade toluene, methanol, acetone and hydrochloric acid, 35% and molecular sieve (4 Å), sodium borohydride were purchased from Merck Specialities Private Limited and used without further purification. C, H and N microanalyses were performed by a Perkin-Elmer 2400II elemental analyzer. FT-IR spectra (KBr disc) were recorded in the range 4000-

400 cm^{-1} on a Shimadzu FT-IR-8400S spectrophotometer. UV-Vis spectra (in CH_3CN) were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer, 300 MHz NMR spectra (in CDCl_3 with TMS as the reference) on a Bruker DPX300 spectrometer and ESI mass spectrum (in CH_3OH) on a Qtof Micro YA263 spectrometer.

Electrochemical measurement :

Cyclic voltammetric (CV) experiments were performed under nitrogen in dry and degassed CH_3CN at a scan rate of 100 mV s^{-1} on a BAS Epsilon electrochemical workstation at 293 K. The conventional three-electrode assembly is comprised of a 1 mm BAS Pt disk working electrode, a platinum-wire auxiliary electrode and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode. The supporting electrolyte is *n*-Bu₄NClO₄ (0.1 M). The analyte concentration was 1.1 mM in CH_3CN .

X-Ray crystallography :

Data for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{21}\text{F}_6\text{FeN}_2\text{P}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($[\text{LH}_2]\text{PF}_6\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were collected at 125 K with a Rigaku Saturn diffractometer using the graphite monochromated Mo- $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The crystal and experimental data are tabulated in Table 1. Intensity data were collected using narrow width ω steps accumulating area detector frames

Table 1. Crystallographic data for $[\text{LH}_2]\text{PF}_6\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{OFeF}_6\text{P}$
Formula weight	484.20
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/c$
Unit cell dimensions :	
<i>a</i> (Å)	20.037(9)
<i>b</i> (Å)	9.398(5)
<i>c</i> (Å)	10.252(5)
β (°)	99.458(11)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1904.1(16)
<i>Z</i>	4
<i>T</i> (K)	125(2)
<i>D</i> _{calcd.} (mg m ⁻³)	1.689
<i>F</i> (000)	992
λ (Mo- $\text{K}\alpha$) (Å)	0.71073
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.946
Total data, unique data, <i>R</i> _{int}	10253, 3341, 0.0534
Observed data [<i>I</i> > 2.0 σ (<i>I</i>)]	3839
Goodness of fit on <i>F</i> ²	3.165
<i>R</i> ₁ (<i>F</i> _o) ^a	0.2133
<i>R</i> _w (<i>F</i> _o ²) ^b	0.6018
^a $R_1 = \sum F_o - F_c / \sum F_o $. ^b $R_w = [\sum (w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2) / \sum w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$.	

spanning at least a hemisphere of reciprocal space for all structures. Data were integrated using the Crystal Clear program. All data were corrected for Lorentz polarization and long-term intensity fluctuations. Absorption effects were corrected on the basis of multiple equivalent reflections and by semi-empirical methods. The structure was solved by direct methods and refined by full-matrix least-squares methods on *F*² using SHELXL¹⁴. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. H atoms were geometrically fixed and allowed to ride on their respective parent atoms. Selected bond distances, bond angles and hydrogen bonds are given respectively in Tables 2 to 3. All calculations were carried out using SHELX-97, PLATON-99¹⁵ and ORTEP¹⁶ programmes.

CCDC reference number CCDC 763786.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (deg.) for complex $[\text{LH}_2]\text{PF}_6\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Fe1-C17	2.022(13)	Fe1-C11	2.024(14)
Fe1-C20	2.031(17)	Fe1-C12	2.038(14)
Fe1-C16	2.043(14)	Fe1-C15	2.046(12)
Fe1-C18	2.052(11)	Fe1-C13	2.062(13)
Fe1-C14	2.073(13)	N1-C2	1.314(18)
N1-C6	1.349(19)	C2-C3	1.373(19)
C2-C7	1.523(19)	C3-C4	1.33(3)
C7-C8	1.549(17)	C8-N9	1.565(13)
N9-C10	1.551(18)	P1-F4	1.554(10)
P1-F6	1.628(9)	-	-
C17-Fe1-C11	129.0(5)	C17-Fe1-C20	67.2(6)
C11-Fe1-C20	115.3(7)	C17-Fe1-C12	109.0(6)
C17-Fe1-C19	67.6(6)	N1-C2-C7	116.7(11)
N1-C6-C5	119.1(14)	N1-C6-H6A	120.5
C10-N9-C8	113.9(10)	C8-N9-H9B	108.8
C13-Fe1-C14	39.1(6)	C2-N1-C6	118.9(13)
F4-P1-F6	176.2(5)	F5-P1-F6	92.2(8)
F3-P1-F6	92.0(7)	F2-P1-F6	87.2(6)

Table 3. Intermolecular hydrogen bonds (Å, deg.) for $[\text{LH}_2]\text{PF}_6\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$

D-H...A	d(D-H)	d(H...A)	d(D...A)	D-H-A
N9-H9A...O1	0.98	2.02	2.91(6)	149.4
N9-H9A...F1	0.98	2.28	2.894(15)	119.9
N9-H9B...F6#1	0.98	2.00	2.906(16)	152.0
N9-H9B...F2#1	0.98	2.12	2.883(19)	134.0

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms :

#1x, -y+1/2, z-1/2

Synthesis :**Preparation of LH :**

214 mg (1.00 mmol) of FCAL was dissolved in 20 ml of toluene containing 500 mg of 4 Å molecular sieves (MS4A). To this dark red solution, 0.12 ml (1.00 mmol) of 2-(2-aminoethyl)pyridine was added. The resulting reaction mixture was heated under refluxing for 9 h. Then it was filtered and the filtrate was left in the air for slow evaporation. After 3 days, a brown pasty mass was obtained. Yield : 0.232 g (73%).

Reduction of LH :

232 mg (0.70 mmol) of LH was dissolved in 10 ml of methanol at room temperature. To this dark red solution 190 mg (5.02 mmol) of solid NaBH₄ was added all at a time with stirring. Immediately a vigorous effervescence was started which subsided slowly. After 15 min of stirring, the pH of the solution was found to be in between 9–10. The color of the reduced mass was light yellow.

Preparation of [LH₂]Cl.H₂O :

To the reduced LH, 5 ml of 4 (N) HCl was added drop wise with constant stirring. The pH at the end of stirring was 5–6 and the color again little bit darkened. It was left in the air for slow evaporation. When the volume reduced to ca. 5 ml, the brownish salt that appeared was filtered and washed thoroughly with solvent ether and was vacuum dried. Yield : 140 mg (54%).

Conversion of [LH₂]Cl.H₂O to [LH₂]PF₆.H₂O :

140 mg (0.30 mmol) of the chloro salt was suspended in 30 ml of acetone on stirring and the reaction mixture was dark grey. Then 130 mg (0.80 mmol) of NH₄PF₆ was added to the mixture all at a time to stir it for 3 h. The mixture was then evaporated nearly to dryness in the air. Filtered and the residue was thoroughly washed with water and the yellow water extract was left in the air for slow evaporation. A dirty yellow compound was obtained that was washed with water and the yellow water extract was left in the air. A dirty yellow compound was obtained that was washed firstly with little water and then thoroughly with solvent ether and was vacuum dried. A dirty yellow powder was obtained. Yield : 40 mg (22%).

Shining red single crystals suitable for X-ray crystal structure determination were obtained by direct diffusion of petroleum ether (40–60) in a moderately concentrated

solution of the salt in dichloromethane. The elemental microanalyses of the single crystals confirm [LH₂]PF₆.H₂O (Found : C, 45.06; H, 4.25; N, 5.84. C₁₈H₂₃N₂OFePF₆ requires : C, 44.60; H, 4.78; N, 5.78%); FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν 839, 558 (PF₆), ν 3255 (NH), ν 3474 (OH), ν 1459 (pyridine ring), ν 1420, 1105 (C–C) and ν 481 (ring tilt of Fe–Cp); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) δ [ppm] : 8.43 (1H, d), 7.71 (1H, t), 7.21 (1H, t), 7.19 (1H, d), 4.43 (2H, d), 4.28 (2H, t, Fc ring), 4.24 (5H, Cp), 4.18 (2H), 3.48 (2H, s), 3.20 (2H, s); ESI-MS, m/z : 519.0216, 321.0515, 198.9863; UV-Vis [CH₃CN, λ_{max}/nm (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 428 (137), 319 (164), 221 (3773).

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